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D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
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Executive summary

Work Package 2 (WP2), “Common Standards, Procedures and Practices” is a core WP for the VITALISE project as it handles all the work and implementation for the Harmonization procedure that is being followed. Within this scope, WP2 attempts to define a methodology for managing the Harmonization activities performed in the project but also guide the Harmonization process of living labs in other domains beyond the VITALISE project. This document aims to present the evaluation process and tools of VITALISE from a twofold perspective:

1. On one hand, present the Harmonization process that will be followed throughout VITALISE along with the events performed and tools used for the Harmonization methodology improvement.
2. On the other hand, present the work of Task 2.2 towards developing an evaluation process and tools for supporting living labs in reaching higher maturity levels while providing them with harmonized tools to do so.

The VITALISE Harmonization methodology was initially developed and presented in D2.1. This deliverable presents the updated version of the methodology which was tested (M6-M12) in order to understand and identify existing difficulties and improve accordingly. The updated version of the methodology is based on the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) and Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA), but is also underpinned on agile development principles. The idea is that every six months a whole Sprint cycle is performed. During each Sprint there are ongoing activities that serve the objectives of the Standard and aim to improve and deliver specific items of the Standard. The events described in the VITALISE Harmonization methodology are:

- Co-creation, to explore and identify new procedures or Standard items that have not been mapped before
- Consensus, to come to an agreement about the harmonization process among the members of the Harmonization Body
- Approval Process, to Approve and Publish the current version of the Standard
- Implement, for Living Labs to adopt and implement in their practice the current approved and public Standard
- Revise & Adjust, to reflect on the feedback and KPIs collected during the implementation Phase for each of the services and procedures

The Harmonization process should be monitored in order to understand if the Standard Versions that are produced are serving their objective of facilitating and improving the access for external researchers to Health and Wellbeing living lab research infrastructures but also if the Standard improve the way that living labs collaborate and work together towards improved outcomes. The Harmonization monitoring is being done in two fronts: 1) monitoring the effectiveness of the process, 2) monitoring the effectiveness of the results.

Within Task 2.2 the VITALISE envisages to create a structured measurement for living labs that will be used so that each living lab can self-evaluate its strengths and weaknesses. In short, the following steps were integrated in the plan of action for the development of the evaluation framework: literature review, ENoLL certification & evaluation framework, collection and evaluation existing self-assessment toolboxes/approaches for living labs, interactive workshop with VITALISE partners, scoping of criteria with group of living lab experts and validation workshop with a specially created pilot group. The concluded evaluation framework is composed by:

- **The strategy of a LL:** with the elements of governance, business model and culture of the living lab
- **Operations of the LL:** with the elements of operations, human resources and equipment & infrastructure
- **Openness of the LL:** with the elements of innovation processes & partnerships and ownership of results

- **Users & reality:** with the elements of quality of the iterative living lab processes in real-life settings, user-centricity of the user & stakeholder engagement approach and the quality of the participatory tools & methods
- **Impact & value creation:** with the elements of co-created values and impacts of the living lab
- **Stability & harmonization:** with the elements of stability of the living lab and harmonization & scale-up

Finally, the consortium is striving throughout VITALISE to have an iterative approach for the evaluation of the procedures within the project (Harmonization methodology) but also beyond the project (the evaluation of all living labs). The approach of a continuous evaluation throughout the remaining duration of the project will allow us to have more concrete feedback, taking into account the possible difficulties and risks.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP2

Work Package 2 (WP2), “Common Standards, Procedures and Practices” is a core WP for the VITALISE project as it handles all the work and implementation for the Harmonization procedure that is being followed. Some of the main tasks is the establishment of the harmonization procedures within the consortium and beyond, the management and organization of the Harmonization procedure events (Harmonization Body and Board meetings) and the definition and update of the Standards and Harmonization methodology by identifying and documenting the existing Living Lab processes, and the similarities and differences among the consortium’s Living Lab partners. The Standard Versions of living labs are documents that try to identify and describe the structure and processes of living lab in an easy to use and comprehensible way. The Standard Versions will be updated every six months until the end of VITALISE project.

Within this scope, WP2 attempts to define a methodology for managing the Harmonization activities performed in the project but also guide the Harmonization process of living labs in other domains beyond the VITALISE project. Furthermore, VITALISE consortium hopes that the living lab Standard will enable the living lab research infrastructures to operate in a more effective way and enhance their collaborations with the research community and the industry. That is why WP2 also builds an evaluation framework for living lab that will be able to track these advances in the living lab community.

1.2 Scope of the document

This document aims to present the evaluation process and tools of VITALISE from a twofold perspective:

3. On one hand, present the Harmonization process that will be followed throughout VITALISE along with the events performed and tools used for the Harmonization methodology improvement.
4. On the other hand, present the work of Task 2.2 towards developing an evaluation process and tools for supporting living labs in reaching higher maturity levels while providing them with harmonized tools to do so.

Continuous monitoring of the two pillars is important as it will allow for continuous improvement that will allow optimization of the Living Lab procedures. Consequently this will result in better services and infrastructures provided in the research community.

1.3 Document structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the WP2 of VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** discusses the Harmonization methodology and the activities and tools related to the monitoring of the methodology.
- **Section 3** presents the work that has been done so far as well as the plan of action for the creation of an evaluation framework for living labs.
- **Section 4** provides some concluded remarks for this deliverable

2 Harmonization process methodology and monitoring

The VITALISE Harmonization methodology was initially developed and presented in D2.1. This version was an initial draft that is further improved and presented in this deliverable. Throughout M6-M12, the steps of the Harmonization methodology were tested in order to understand and identify existing difficulties and improve accordingly. The updated version of the VITALISE Harmonization methodology is presented below.

2.1 Description of Harmonization methodology

VITALISE, leveraging on the concept of Design Thinking which starts from an existing problem to be explored, sets the current status of the Living Labs. The iterative process of VITALISE is based on the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) and Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA). Each iteration will take place every 6 months and the outcome will be a new Standard Version deliverable (D2.1, D2.3-D2.7).

The initial version of the VITALISE Harmonization methodology is depicted in Figure 1. The first linear (State of the art) phase is the one performed in Task 2.1 and reported in D2.1. The initial idea was that a full cycle will be repeated every 6 months and the outcome will be the deliverable of the Standard Version (D2.3-D2.7). During the lifecycle of a full cycle, more than one components (service or procedures to be harmonized) go through.

Figure 1 Harmonization framework

However, due to the complexity of each component in the living lab management system followed by the VITALISE standards (see D2.1), the realization of a whole circle for each component was not proven feasible. VITALISE Harmonization needs a more flexible approach that will enable each activity to be performed at different pace and using different tools. The updated version of the methodology is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Refined Harmonization framework

The updated version of the methodology is based on the PDCA/PDSA but is also underpinned on agile development principles. VITALISE harmonization methodology borrows some ideas from the SRUM framework in order to organize the overall semester iterations, the so-called Sprints. The idea is that every six months a whole Sprint cycle is performed. During each Sprint there are ongoing activities that serve the objectives of the Standard and aim to improve and deliver specific items of the Standard. For example, Standard v0.2 (D2.3) focus on the update of data and devices taxonomy. The activities for the update of a specific item follow the methodological framework presented in Figure 1. This framework is not followed in a strict and definite way but instead serves as guidelines of what are the steps to be followed so that an item can be considered ready for delivery.

Figure 3 Update of Standard Items across time

At the end of the Sprint, each concluded item that has ready outcomes can be included in the next Standard Version. In the other case that the lifecycle of an item lasts more than the Sprint duration, it continues to the next Sprint. At the end of each Sprint, only the concluded items will be considered by the Harmonization Body/Board for revision and approval.

Due to the iterative nature of the Harmonization process and the empirical improvement of the methodology, VITALISE Harmonization methodology borrows events from SCRUM in order to improve the process. Right after every new Standard version release, starting from this version (D2.3 Standard Version 2) onwards, two events are being performed.

Next Standard objectives definition

This event is inspired by the Sprint Planning of SCRUM framework. During the Next Standard objectives definition, the VITALISE team leading the Harmonization process will define the following items:

- Agree on the sprint objective, a short description of what they forecast to deliver in the next Standard Version,
- Select the Standard components (items) that contribute towards this objective and are in line with the project activities
- Form a plan by mutually discussing and agreeing on which parts of the Standard will be updated at the current Standard Version.
- Finally, take into account the non-concluded standard components that will be inherited by the previous Sprint

A draft planning of the objectives and related project activities is presented in the table below. However, the goal is to redefine this table based on the outcomes of each iteration of Standard Version.

Table 1 Harmonization Objectives and related project activities

Standard and delivery date	Objective	Related project activities
Standard Version 2 – March 2022 [M12]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and devices updated version • First version of lexicon (collection of terms) • Updated wiki page structure Living Lab Business Model updates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of user requirements (data and devices related) • Refinement of JRAs protocols • First open call for external researchers
Standard Version 3 – September 2022 [M18]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revised version of ethics harmonized documents • Lexicon definitions • Research process stages • Refinement of services of the exploration and co-creation phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open calls • Panel management release • Co-creation sessions of JRAs • Deployment procedures for JRAS • 1st summer school
Standard Version 4 – March 2023 [M24]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lexicon definitions • Refinement of services of the real life testing phase and infrastructure and data management phase • Update of research process stages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st round of visits of external researchers are finalized • Execution of JRAs activities
Standard Version 5 – September 2023 [M30]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LL business model updates • Innovation process definition • Refinement of services of the support on market uptake 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2nd round of visits of external researchers are finalized • JRAs data are collected • 2nd summer school
Standard Version 6 – March 2024 [M36]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LL business model with input from external researchers • Innovation process updates • Refinement of services of the legal, financial and administrative support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3rd round of visits is finalized

Methodology evaluation

VITALISE Harmonization methodology is envisioned to be an empirical framework for living lab harmonization that is tested and refined during VITALISE. The methodology at the end of the VITALISE project should be ready to be adopted by other living lab clusters (domains other than Health and Wellbeing) in order to identify and harmonize any additional services that they might have. As an empirical framework, it is important to constantly gather feedback to improve it. This can be done during the Methodology Evaluation Event, borrowed from the Sprint retrospective of the SCRUM framework. During the Methodology Evaluation Event the team:

- reflects on the past sprint(s)
- inspects how the last Sprint went (individuals, interactions, processes, tools)
- identifies and agrees on continuous process improvement actions

Three suggested areas to consider in methodology evaluation are:

- What went well during the sprint?
- What did not go well?
- What could we do differently the next sprint?

For the time being, the activities for the update of each item will remain the same. Some small modifications are included in the descriptions below to better serve all the items that are developed in the Standard. The idea is that the specific events described below are not strictly implemented and their order could change, or events can be repeated during a cycle. However, they serve as guidelines of steps for external stakeholders that would like to replicate the process. During each Methodology Evaluation Event, the activities of the cycle can also be updated.

Co-Creation

Explanation/Objective: The objective of this step is to explore and identify new procedures or Standard items that have not been mapped before and do not appear in any of the previous standard versions. In the co-creation phase we explore the input that cannot be mapped in an existing category or the restructure of the living lab management system and Standard structure. The co-creation also includes the redefinition and improvement of existing items in the Standard. The discussion on the existing and “implemented” procedures will be done by taking into account the report with proposed updates for the Living Labs services, procedures and methods (the output of the “Revise and Adjust” phase). It is essential to include a multifaceted group, with different skillsets & perspectives, to build on each other’s ideas. Thus, this phase requires the participation of living labs and stakeholders to work together towards eliciting information about emerging but also existing living lab procedures, services and methods.

Input: The co-creation phase will take as input the objectives that are defined in the “Next Standard objectives definition” event. Taking into account the specific objectives a discussion will be carried out (either online through tools such as Miro/mentimeter, or physical meeting) where both living labs and stakeholders will be invited. The topic of the discussion will focus on the feedback gathered during the “Revise & Adjust phase” and how this can be validated to reach consensus and approval.

Output/Outcome: An updated list of items that will be fed to consensus process, including the potential addition of unmapped items so far. An initial description for each of the new items will be drafted based on the outputs and outcomes of this step.

Sample Group: Harmonization Body (internal, external living labs and stakeholders)

Events (Implementation steps):

1. Co-creation process through open discussion (meeting or workshop) or open deliberation tool (wiki comments, eDelphi tool)

Tools to be used:

1. Miro (in case of online), boards and post-its (in case of physical meetings)
2. eDelphi tool
3. comments on wiki-page

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- participation of more than 10 Living Labs
- participation of 20 Stakeholders (researchers, etc.), as identified by the harmonization procedure

Possible Risks: Bringing living labs and stakeholders at the same session to have a multifaceted group (cannot take place offline). Manage to integrate all Living Labs into this process in order to be aware of new research and innovations.

Consensus

Explanation/Objective: To come to an agreement about the harmonization process among the members of the Harmonization Body but also among the members of the Harmonization Board (voting). This step aims to create a consensus for a current version of an item, based on the outcomes of the co-creation phase. By dictionary definition the term consensus is “a generally accepted opinion or decision among a group of people” (Cambridge Dictionary). However, there is no universally accepted decision rules to define when the consensus has been reached. Common approaches are simple majority and supermajority. A simple majority is reached when 50% of the voters support the decision or opinion whereas common supermajority thresholds are typically 90%, 80%, 75%, 70% or two thirds. In the Table 2 consensus level interpretations during the VITALISE living lab harmonization decision making are presented.

Table 2 Consensus level interpretation during the VITALISE living lab harmonization decision making

Consensus level of the voters	Agreement interpretation	Color code
Over or equal to 80%	Strong supermajority agreement	
Over or equal to 70% but less than 80%	Supermajority agreement	
Over or equal to 50%, but less than 70%	Simple majority agreement	
Over or equal to 30%, but less than 50%	Simple majority disagreement	
Less than 30%	Supermajority disagreement	

The items presented in living lab research infrastructure standard (e.g. a method name and description), should achieve at least supermajority agreement level among VITALISE consortium living labs and Harmonization Body before they can be officially included into the revised and published standard. Items achieving at least simple majority level are considered as “candidates” and are made publicly available as part of standard with “candidate remark” in order to stimulate public debate. All items below 50% agreement will have to go under new development rounds and are considered as working progress items. These items are not included into standard documents. For items that a quantitative measure is not possible to be acquired, the qualitative consensus rules are being defined up-front in the co-creation phase with the approval of at least the simple majority of the Harmonization Body. The rules for consensus are susceptible to changes during the Methodology Evaluation event.

Input: The description and the template that have come out of the Co-creation, as well as the previous Revise and Adjust phase.

Output/Outcome: The level of agreement (consensus) for all the procedures and services that have gone through the implementation phase or the emerging ones that came out from the Co-creation phase.

Sample Group: Harmonization Body or Harmonization Board

Events (Implementation steps):

- Identify conflicts (based on definition)
- Discuss conflicts
- Come to a consensus

Tools to be used:

- common workshop
- four-point Likert scale including strongly disagree, disagree, agree, strongly agree
- eDelphi study evaluation and analysis stage
- crowdsourcing – crowd rating (can be used occasionally)

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- Consensus from 80% or over of the Harmonization Body/Board = Excellent
- Consensus from 70% but less than 80% of the Harmonization Body = Good
- Consensus from 50% but less than 70% of the Harmonization Body/Board = Poor
- Consensus from less than 50% of the Harmonization Body/Board = Rejected

Possible Risks: Not finding common ground and achieving consensus

Approval Process

Explanation/Objective: To Approve and Publish the current version of the Standard that came out of the Consensus after going through a Public Review event for final comments. The approval process is being performed by the Harmonization Board after they have undergone the consensus process from the whole Harmonization Body.

Input: The items with supermajority consensus from the Consensus Phase, or less if Harmonization Body/Board agrees to do so. The items that have reached a consensus through quantitative rules defined by the Harmonization Body.

Output/Outcome: The Standard version for the current iteration.

Sample Group: Harmonization Board

Events (Implementation steps):

- Public Review: an event that involves the public in providing their views and feedback on the consensus to consider in decision-making. The items with supermajority consensus, along with all the information and the harmonized data) become publicly accessible for a certain period. The platform that will support the sharing of the proposed Standard allows everyone to provide

feedback, comments or even to raise potential objections in an anonymous manner. From VITALISE, the corresponding website section with comments enabled, will be used.

- Approve: The Harmonization Board meets to review the comments and feedback received during the Public Review, making adaptations and approving the current version
- Publish: The final event includes the dissemination of the results of the harmonization process and the Standard version at the official site of the VITALISE project as well as 2 more social media channels

Tools to be used:

- meeting of the Harmonization Board (physical or online)
- websites and mailing lists
- Platform with comment enabled functionality for the Public Review event

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- Published on 3 websites (VITALISE, ENoLL, Forum LLSA)
- Disseminate the published version to mailing list and social media

Possible Risks: Risk of losing added value, information that would be important for some and pose problems for others

Implement

Explanation/Objective: Implementation of the research activities from all the Living Labs involved. Living Labs are invited to adopt the current approved and public Standard, focusing more (if possible) on the new services and modifications that the current standard has introduced. To do so, the living labs should be involving the proper stakeholders to use the provided services and procedures. For VITALISE, the stakeholders are the researchers of the JRAs along with the selected researchers for Transnational Access.

Input: The current approved and published Standard

Output/Outcome: The information/feedback collected from the Living Labs after the implementation of the of the research activities

Sample Group: Stakeholders using Living Labs' harmonized services and procedures

Events (Implementation steps):

- Planning by choosing the services that will be deployed in the consortium LL
- Period for implementation
- Feedback collection from the living labs

Tools to be used: digital platform for reporting KPIs and feedback, (e.g., google forms), self-assessment grid

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- Quantitative questionnaire for Standard version (questions about usefulness, usability, presentation, level of applicability, services that are not included)
- Self-evaluation framework for living labs (see Section 3)

Possible Risks: Risk that living labs do not recognize themselves in the self-assessment grid and in the score assigned according to their activities

Revise & Adjust

Explanation/Objective: To reflect on the feedback and KPIs collected during the implementation Phase for each of the services and procedures. To understand better what has worked and what has not gone well in order to propose adjustments for the harmonized service or procedure that could lead to better KPIs.

Input: Documents/lists completed from the Living Labs (about the number and description of the existing services, processes, use cases examples, tools etc.) and KPIs from the “Implement” phase

Output/Outcome: A report with proposed updates for the Living Labs services, processes and methods.

Sample Group: Harmonization Body

Events (Implementation steps):

Tools to be used:

4. Interviews, mostly with Living Labs to understand what they have done
5. Analysis of the KPIs (quantitative and qualitative)

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- Interview at least 70% of LL that participated in the “Implement” phase

Possible Risks: Difficulties in communication/lack of time for performing the interviews, difficulties in reaching common terminology about use cases and provided services/methodologies among the stakeholders (Living Labs).

2.2 Description of Harmonization monitoring tools

The Harmonization process should be monitored in order to understand if the Standard Versions that are produced are serving their objective of facilitating and improving the access for external researchers to Health and Wellbeing living lab research infrastructures but also if the Standard improve the way that living labs collaborate and work together towards improved outcomes. The Harmonization monitoring is being done in two fronts: 1) monitoring the effectiveness of the process, 2) monitoring the effectiveness of the results.

2.2.1 Monitoring the Harmonization process

The monitoring of the Harmonization process will take place during the Methodology Evaluation Event after each standard release. It will be done basically from the core Harmonization team consisting of VITALISE partners. It will be based on a self-assessment questionnaire that is inspired by the work done in the SIMPLA H2020 project¹. The main steps are:

- Individual Living Labs to use the “SELF ASSESSMENT QUESTIONNAIRE” (ANNEX 1)
- Check the results with Harmonization Body
- Check the results with the decision maker (living lab networks and Harmonization Board)
- Write the harmonization report (part of Standard Version Deliverable)

¹ <http://www.simpla-project.eu/en/>

- Discuss “lessons learned” with the harmonization team to improve the process for the next time.

The harmonization activities and their monitoring processes are performed in parallel. As the harmonization methodology is designed in an agile way, while the harmonization activities take place its progress is being monitored so that corrective actions can be made if considered necessary. The corrective actions aim to act proactively in order to improve future executions and avoid repeating same procedures that are not effective. The monitoring is performed once in every Sprint, however some steps of the evaluation that have not changed can remain the same from the previous Sprint.

2.2.2 Monitoring the Harmonization outcomes

The monitoring of the Harmonization outcomes will have two main pillars:

1. Are the living labs performing activities in a more efficient way and do the Standard produced help them operate in a improved way and collaborate more easily? This will be assessed by the evaluation framework for living labs. It is envisioned that the Standard could help living labs improve their scoring in the evaluation framework across the lifecycle of the project
2. Is the Standard useful, easy to be used, understandable acceptable and easily applicable by external researchers that would like to use living lab infrastructures and service for their research? This will be assessed mainly by the external research that will join VITALISE research infrastructures for Transnational access visits. It will be assessed by a qualitative and quantitative questionnaire that will be co-created with the Harmonization Body on the next Standard iteration.

3 A structured evaluation framework for living labs

Within Task 2.2 the VITALISE envisages to create a structured measurement for living labs that will be used so that each living lab can self-evaluate its strengths and weaknesses. A multi-method research approach (Brewer and Hunter, 2006) was applied, considering multiple sources of existing evidence of evaluation structures, building blocks and criteria for living labs.

In short, the following steps were integrated in the plan of action for the development of the evaluation framework:

1. Literature review (including the 3-layered living lab model from Schuurman (2015))
2. ENoLL certification & evaluation framework
3. Collection and evaluation existing self-assessment toolboxes/approaches for living labs
4. Interactive workshop with VITALISE partners
5. Scoping of criteria with group of living lab experts
6. Validation workshop with a specially created pilot group

Following these steps, the pilot group mentioned here above will continue to support the VITALISE project to further define & refine the necessary Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) and scoring tables, towards the creation of a structured framework for living labs. Finally, they will be involved into to co-creation and co-design of the VITALISE self-assessment tool over the remaining time of the project. This section presents in more details the already performed steps towards the creation of the final framework.

3.1 Literature review

First, a literature review on existing evaluation frameworks and wider definitions of living labs including criteria was conducted by searching academic literature as well as European funded living lab projects and living networks websites and publications (e.g., project reports, membership application guidelines, gray papers). The search terms included in the title the term "*living lab(s)*" and the term "*evaluation*" or "*criteria*" or "*assessment*". The identified evaluation frameworks were studied to identify the criteria used by the research community for defining the living labs, defining "a preliminary set of criteria" (Forsström 2020, Mulder 2008, Mulder 2007).

A list of the previously identified criteria (Forsström 2020, Mulder 2008, Mulder 2007) includes:

- openness within the organisation's strategy
- collaborative culture
- policies for publication
- copyright and proprietary rights
- licensing
- policies for research data and other research outputs
- developing and maintaining competences
- access to infrastructures
- promoting interoperability
- governance
- experience in living lab operations
- innovation methodology
- iterative living lab approach
- real-life settings
- stakeholders' active involvement
- quality of methods and tools
- qualified staff
- communication strategy
- value for all involved stakeholders
- business model

One of the most important sources found for the harmonization process to reach an evaluation framework described in this deliverable is the 3-layered living lab model as described in Schuurman's PhD dissertation (2015): Bridging the gap between Open and User Innovation? Exploring the value of Living Labs as a means to structure user contribution and manage distributed innovation. This model is being used by ENoLL(see 2.2.2) ever since to define and explain living labs. Schuurman (2015) has proposed a widely-used macro-meso-micro level approach for classifying living lab studies. The **Macro level** was described as the living lab's network consisting of different stakeholders that engage in knowledge transfers, mainly around an innovative infrastructure (material and/or immaterial). The **Meso level** was referring to the innovation projects and activities

carried out within a living lab while the **Micro level** focused more on the living lab methodological steps and the tools used.

However, despite its value in classifying living labs, the suggested three level analysis approach has not yet been adopted to any of the existing living lab evaluation frameworks, which are mainly focusing on meso- and/or micro-levels. The limitations in evaluation process constrain the development of the living lab movement as well as hinders the possibilities to find the secret receipt for sustainable living lab business model (Santonen et al. 2020). Furthermore, Mastelic et al. (2015) argued that limited attention has been currently paid on how such an evaluation contributes to living lab performance while the need to better understand the various facets of living labs and find effective management approaches has also been raised by other LL authors (e.g., Hossain et al. 2019).

3.2 ENoLL current certification and evaluation framework

European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) is an international non-profit membership-based association promoting and enhancing the Living Labs concept globally. ENoLL can be considered as the leading global living lab authority due having the world's largest membership network. All new candidate living labs must undergo a quality assessment process to make sure that all members meet their living lab standards, based on an existing ENoLL evaluation framework.

Since 2007, ENoLL has evaluated and certified over 500 living labs, based on that evolutionary framework which is regularly revised by their labelling & certification task force to make sure new (academic) insights are captured within the framework. Over the last 15 years they managed to bring down the necessary criteria to evaluate living labs from over 28 to 15 (general) criteria that apply to all types of living labs. Furthermore, in 2020, they introduced weighted criteria in 3 categories to make sure crucial elements count more heavenly.

There are 3 different types of criteria:

- **A-criteria:** *these criteria are essential in the definition of a living lab and therefore get a weight of 15 points for each criterion*
- **B-criteria:** *these criteria are important in the definition of a living lab and therefore get a weight of 10 points for each criterion*
- **C-criteria:** *these criteria are a valuable add-on to the previous A & B criteria and therefore get a weight of 5 points for each criterion*

The whole current criteria of ENoLL are divided over 6 chapters. These chapters focus on the main aspects of living lab operations (essential building blocks of a living lab).

Below you can find the 6 chapters and their 15 weighted criteria

Table 3 Chapters and weighted criteria

Chapter	Criteria
Organization	Organization, management & governance of the living lab (A) Experience in living lab operations (B) Interest to participate in regional or (inter)national innovation system mechanisms (C)
Users & reality	An iterative living lab process & real-life setting (A) Users & people engagement approach (B) Quality of methods & tools (C)
Resources	Roles & responsibilities of qualified staff (A) Access & availability of equipment & infrastructures Internal & external communication (C)

Openness	Openness of innovation processes and partnerships (A) Feedback protection & author's rights (C)
Value	Co-created values for all involved stakeholders (A) Coverage of the value chain (C)
Business model and plans for the future	Business Model & access/ability to funding (A) SWOT analysis & strategic plans for the future (B)

Finally, ENoLL created general scoring tables for each of the criteria, to support applicants and evaluators towards a common understanding about them.

However, looking at the way living labs are defined and being evaluated currently within different living lab networks, like European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) and Le Forum des Living Labs en Santé et Autonomie (Forum LLSA) (see Figure 6) the macrolevel aspects (e.g., impact and effectiveness) are underrepresented from the frameworks which are being used. Therefore, it's still hard to measure the maturity of living labs in relation to the 3 layered living labs model (*Schuurman, 2015*) and evaluate the sustainability of living labs. Starting from this existing evaluation framework, the next step within task 2.2 was to match the ENoLL chapters and criteria with the list of KPI's. Below you can find the matching table. Areas marked in black are missing on their side of the matching.

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

ENOLL			VITALISE	
CHAPTERS	CRITERIAS	KPI's	KPI's	CRITERIAS
Organization	Organization, management & governance of the living lab	quadruple helix, governance model, roles & responsibilities present in governance, stakeholders involved in management		
	Experience in living lab operations	living lab projects, living lab activities, years of experience	Participation of stakeholders to any activities in x of y (%)	Type an amount of activities per year where you involve the different type of stakeholders (via grid/ matrix)
			Number of stakeholders participating	Amount of stakeholder groups (type citizens, type of patients, type of caregivers, type of care organisations etc)
			involvement of actors from the quadruple helix -> have more precise categories	Mapping the degree of knowledge exchange among network actors (fostering exchange)
Interest & ability to participate in regional or (inter)national innovation system mechanisms	involvement in open innovation ecosystems, projects & proposals	Number of partners involved	Number of common deliverables (commonly produced by all partners)	
Users & Reality	An iterative living lab process & real-life settings	iterative approach, lifecycle approach, real life settings & daily life of users	User taking part during the research design phase	PRE
			pre-evaluation of the level of user centric before doing the study	
	Users & people engagement approach	ways of involvement of users, level of involvement & decision power of users	real case studies	Case studies
			Size of the permanent panel and research participant	PRE
			Has permanent panel	
			Diversity and profiles of the panel members and participants in the research	
	Quality of methods & tools	range of used methods, range of used (co-creation) tools, quality of these methods & tools	Impact of user input (did users feedbacks had impact solution)	POST
			Reprensativity of the panel regarding the targetted population	DURING
	Roles & responsibilities of qualified staff	time allocated to the different roles in the LL team, qualification & experience of the personnel	Intensity/ degree of the user participation (scale from theoretical studies from non participation to users as co-decision makers)	
			Number of workshops	
Number of participants in the workshops			Courses	
Professional academic courses for "students"				
Professional training courses for stakeholders			POST	
variety of stakeholders in knowledge sharing activities				Variety of actors
Number of user taking part of the study	POST			
Common users descriptions profiles	PRE			
Resources	Access & availability of equipment & infrastructures	access % to necessary infrastructures (working spaces, co-creation/experimentation spaces, dataplatforms...), availability of necessary equipment (feedback collection tools, analytical feedback tools, interaction tools, toolkits...)	number of experts	Variety of actors
			Total personnel count of each stakeholder	Number of panel mebers following the type of stakeholder groups where you work with
	Internal & external communication	branding, external communication channels, accessibility (how to contact them?), internal communication & collaboration channels & tools, results sharing, knowledge sharing, meeting structures	spectrum of effect of projects and its result on international level	spectrum of effect of projects and its result on international level
(Better) communication between different actors (in the process of rehabilitation)			(Better) communication between different actors (in the process of rehabilitation)	
Number of internal knowledge sharing meetings			Workshops	
Number of researcher exchanges/ stakeholder exchanges			Mapping the degree of knowledge exchange among network actors (fostering exchange)	
Organization in Focus group				

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

ENOLL			VITALISE	
Openness	Openness of innovation processes and partnerships	accessibility for new stakeholders, ways of attracting them, openness of involvement of participating stakeholders & users, openness	Access to the user via partners (e.g collaboration partnership or MOU agreements) # of MOUs with different types duration of coloboration	PRE Amount of stakeholder groups (type citizens, type of patients, type of caregivers, type of care organisations etc)
	Feedback protection & author's rights	levels of author's rights of involved stakeholder, IPR & feedback agreements,		
Value	Co-created values for all involved stakeholders	concrete outcomes of LL activities, impact of the outcomes on the ecosystem, involvement of different types of stakeholders, created value for different types of stakeholders	Participation satisfaction (for participating) of users	POST
			Impact of user "health and wellbeing (I.E os the solution good and do what was promising)	
			number of invited speeches (for the living lab activities)	Variety of actors
			Number of study credits	Courses
			number of students graduating	
			Transnational "autorship (number of living lab athours in your publication)	Publications
			Number of meetings with specif outputs	Qualitative & Quantitative common outcomes - measuring outcomes
			Number of implemented use cases across LL per JRA (transnational/ virtual)	
			number of publications (joint publications)	
	number of common projects			
Coverage of the value chain	engagement level of value chain actors in projects/activities, impact on the value chain created		Number of multiple stakeholders interests/ needs met	Amount of participants (of each stakeholder group) you actually engage in your activities each year
			societal impact in relatio to economic impact (& Business Plan of LLs)	societal impact in relatio to economic impact (& Business Plan of LLs)
			Services that can have societal impact for society (also important for the public services) both social & economic impact	Services that can have societal impact for society (also important for the public services) both social & economic impact
Business Model and Future plans	Business Model & access/ability to funding	access to regional, national or international funding mechanisms, business model, quality of BM		
	SWOT Analysis & strategic plans for the future	strenghts & weaknesses, mid to long term objectives of the LL, concrete plans for the future		
			Researchers satisfaction on the LL harmonised procedures provided	Measure how this harmonization will impact in the quality of contribution by the Living Labs
			number of common procedures	
			number of projects run with commo process	common understanding, about procedures, policies of Living Labs
			Helping each other when we have a problem	
			Number of workshops on common practicies/ sharing experienceies	
			State of the art concerning procedures, policies, contacts	
			Number of co-produced procedures	
			Number of new opend and public standards	

Figure 4 Comparison of ENOLL and VITALISE criteria and KPIs by chapter

3.3 Existing self-assessment toolboxes and approaches

As a third step, the VITALISE living lab management system as developed and presented in D2.1 and two self-assessment approaches were analysed and compared on the level of integrated chapters by analyzing chapters and criteria of these 3 approaches.

The VITALISE living lab management system focuses more on the research aspects of the living lab, but still contains very valuable insights to add to the evaluation framework. Among others by highlighting the importance of Methods and Tools and a living lab business model.

Figure 5 VITALISE living lab management system

The self-assessment approach from Forum LLSA based on the GEMSA grid (GEMSA, grille multidimensionnelle d'auto-évaluation des technologies pour la santé et l'autonomie, Robert Picard and co-constructed in a project in partnership with EIT Health during the Living Labs and test Bed Programme) (Picard, 2018) provides clear building blocks for living labs, and moreover it indicates certain KPIs to measure the maturity of living labs inside their network. Finally, it makes a solid attempt in making all these aspects visually represented. The chapters this Forum LLSA evaluation framework focuses on are:

- Governance
- Strategy and value proposition
- User & stakeholder involvement
- Real-life dimension
- Methodology dimension
- Operational processes
- Human resources dimension
- Financial dimension
- Monitoring/quality management
- Outcomes

Below we present the visual representation of the self-assessment items proposed by Forum LLSA.

Figure 6 – Self assessment grid FORUM LLSA

The second self-assessment tool considered for this task is the PROVAHEALTH self assessment tool (Santonen et al.,2020), developed during the running time of this Interreg Baltic Sea Region project (2017-2020) which is focusing more on the transnational living lab collaboration model, which guides living labs in their approach on how to build lasting setups. Business models for transnational living labs are a combination of both individual and transnational models. This work was integrated into this task because of the relevance of framing a living lab on the macro level beyond the meso project-level and beyond the traditional lifecycle approach of an innovation project (ideation, co-creation, experimentation, validation) by also integrating the implementation phase into their tool. Finally, also this tool offers insights into possible needed KPIs. Based on this approach the self-assessment tool focuses on following steps:

- *Ideas*
- *Conceptualisation*
- *Proof of concept*
- *Validation*
- *Implementation*
- *Finish*

The visual representation used by PROVAHEALTH tool is very similar to the one proposed by Forum LLSA and is presented below.

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

Figure 7 Self-assessment tool of PROVAHEALTH

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

As final part of this step, a matching chapter table was created to discover synergies and differences among the three frameworks described previously.

3 layered model of living labs	ENoLL certification framework	Living Lab Management System	Forum LLSA	Provahealth
MACRO (organization, platform)	Organization	2. Living Lab business model	Governance	Ideas
			Operational outcomes	Validation
		3. Research process	Research	Ideas
		4. Innovation process	Processes & project management	Ideas
		5. R&D services	Research outcomes	Validation
	Users & reality	7. Data collection approaches		Ideas
				Conceptualisation
	Resources	6. Living Lab Research infrastructure	Human Resources	Conceptualisation
			Financial and technical resources	Validation
	Openness	4. Innovation process		Conceptualisation
Value	2. Living Lab business model	Clients/user outcomes	Validation	
		Social outcomes	Implementation	
Business models & plans for the future	2. Living Lab business model	Strategy	Implementation	
		HR outcomes		
MESO (projects & methodologies)	Users & reality	3. Research process	Research	Proof of concept
			Research outcomes	
		7. Data collection approaches	Processes & project management	Proof of concept
	Openness	4. Innovation process	Processes & project management	Validation
	Value	5. R&D services	Research outcomes	
		Clients/user outcomes	Validation	
		Social outcomes		
MICRO (LL activities & research steps)	Users & reality	3. Research process	Research	Proof of concept
			Research outcomes	
		7. Data collection approaches	Processes & project management	Proof of concept
	Openness	4. Innovation process	Processes & project management	Validation
	Value	5. R&D services	Research outcomes	
		Clients/user outcomes	Validation	
		Social outcomes		
		1. Living Lab lexicon - terms & definitions		

Figure 8 Matching table of the three frameworks

3.4 Interactive workshop with VITALISE partners

To validate and further develop the evaluation structure and the necessary KPI's. A first consultation space has been set up to allow members to exchange views on these questions of evaluation tools and methods. the objective is to acculturate members and involve them in a co-construction process. An interactive workshop was organized the 1st of June 2021 with all the VITALISE partners (28 participants) to collect their feedback on the matching and the prepared proposal for chapters by the partners of Task 2.2, based on the project agreement. The proposed list of chapters looked were:

- Access to RIs (transnational and virtual)
- Common understanding (communication)
- Economical impact
- Harmonization of tools, methods & technologies
- Harmonization/standardization of procedures, policies & contracts
- Knowledge sharing & capacity building
- Multi stakeholder approach
- Network Collaboration
- Societal Impact
- User centric approach (quantitative & qualitative)

During an interactive voting via Mentimeter the participants of the workshop were asked to rank the chapters in order of importance to them. The results of this voting are shown here below:

Figure 9 Mentimeter – Workshop 1st of June 2021

The last part of the interactive workshop offered all participants the opportunity to highlight items they were missing in the proposed chapters.

What's missing?

Figure 10 Word cloud – Workshop 1st of June 2021

The inputs from this interactive workshop were important to collect insights before starting to create weighted criteria and to identify possible KPI's who could better support the needs of the Vitalise partners.

3.5 Scoping of the criteria with living lab experts

After the interactive workshop with the VITALISE partners, all inputs and listed items in the framework were consolidated and classified to macro-, meso- and micro layers by a group of living lab researchers & experts (N=15). This group existed out of members of the ENOLL certification & labelling taskforce, living lab researchers, VITALISE partners and members of Forum LLSA. For the classification of the criteria the macro-, meso- and micro- definition of Schuurman (2015) was used. During multiple online sessions (N=3), this team of researchers and experts further scoped and refined the necessary chapters and criteria until they reached consensus.

The evaluation framework they created looks like:

- **The strategy of a LL (macro-level)**
 - a. Governance (macro)
 - i. Shared vision & mission
 - ii. Involvement of quadruple helix actors
 - iii. Team design
 - iv. Expected impacts of LL strategy & LL projects
 - b. business model (macro)
 - i. Financial engineering
 - ii. Service portfolio
 - c. culture of the living lab (macro)
 - i. External collaboration strategies
 - ii. Internal collaboration strategies
 - iii. Internal communication processes
- **Operations of the LL (all levels)**
 - d. Operations
 - i. Experience in LL projects & activities (meso- and micro)
 - ii. Monitoring processes (operational & impact) (macro and meso)
 - iii. Branding and positioning (all)
 - iv. Partner agreements (macro and meso)
 - e. human resources
 - i. Availability and assignment of staff (all)
 - ii. Role fluidity (all)
 - f. equipment & infrastructure
 - i. Access (all)
 - ii. Availability (all)

- **Openness of the LL (all levels)**
 - g. innovation processes & partnerships
 - i. Legal agreements (all)
 - ii. Data agreements (all)
 - iii. Transparency level (all)
 - iv. Openness towards new partnerships (macro)
 - h. ownership of results
 - i. Feedback protection (meso and micro)
 - ii. Types of ownership (meso and micro)
 - iii. IP processes (all)
- **Users & reality (all levels)**
 - i. quality of the iterative living lab processes in real-life settings
 - i. Lifecycle approach and/or LL integrative process (meso)
 - ii. Real -life settings (meso and micro)
 - j. user-centricity of the user & stakeholder engagement approach
 - i. Intensity of user participation & impact (all)
 - ii. Representativity user panel (meso and micro)
 - iii. Permanence user panel (macro)
 - k. the quality of the participatory tools & methods
 - i. Engagement strategies (all)
 - ii. Range tools & methods (all)
 - iii. Quality & innovativeness tools & methods (all)
 - iv. External communication processes (all)
- **Impact & value creation (all levels)**
 - l. co-created values
 - i. User satisfaction (meso and micro)
 - ii. Stakeholder satisfaction (all)
 - iii. Knowledge exchange and sharing (all)
 - iv. Academic validation (macro and meso)
 - v. Capacity building (macro and meso)
 - vi. Value capturing strategies (macro and meso)
 - vii. Value chain coverage (macro and meso)
 - m. impacts of the living lab
 - i. Internal impact (all)
 - ii. Societal impact (all)
 - iii. Economical impact (macro and meso)
 - iv. Environmental impact (macro and meso)
 - v. Regulatory impact (macro and meso)
- **Stability & harmonization (macro-level)**
 - n. stability of the living lab (macro)
 - i. SWOT
 - ii. Improved collaborations
 - iii. Business plan
 - o. harmonization & scale-up (macro)
 - i. Standardized processes, procedures, tools, methods & technologies
 - ii. Replicability
 - iii. Cross-sectoral and cross-border collaboration
 - iv. Benchmark knowledge sharing & capacity building

3.6 Validation workshop with a pilot group

A validation workshop was performed, aiming to validate and further develop the evaluation structure and the necessary KPI's. A pilot group existing out of members of ENoLL and Forum LLSA, together with VITALISE living labs and other interested organizations was created. During an interactive workshop early March 2022, they provided input for the KPI's via an exercise on a Miro Board. The outputs of this interactive workshop should enable the structures to carry out a self-assessment by filling in a grid comprising several Chapters, Criteria, KPI's (see ANNEX 2, *Pilot Group Evaluation Structure*).

4 Conclusions

This task aims to meet one of the project's objectives, which is to have a harmonised process that is SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, Timely). To achieve this, several tools and methodologies have been put in place in the first year of the project in order to quickly have a basis to be tested by all the actors of the project. Continuous measurement of the Harmonization process and methodology will give adequate indications to validate or not the tools created in this first year. The two events of the Harmonization methodology that are borrowed from the SCRUM framework, the Next Standard objective definition and the Methodology Evaluation, are the ones that will set the focus of the Standard and drive the monitoring process. The methodology is foreseen to be implemented in an agile way, and the empirical results of the monitoring process will be integrated in the methodology. The VITALISE Harmonization methodology is also part of the sustainability plan of VITALISE (more details will be included on D13.4) as it is envisaged to be adopted by other group of living labs, operating in different domains, that aim to harmonize their procedures. The final version of the methodology, that will integrate the empirical modifications made during the Methodology evaluation events, will be presented in the final Standard Version 6 (D2.8, M36).

The evaluation framework for living labs is a work in progress that will be further refined after the work with the pilot group has finished. As presented in Figure 11, the work started with the first workshop in June 2021 in which we discussed how to find common standards and procedures on living lab evaluation.

Figure 11 Evaluation and monitoring of Living Labs

The first Working Group meeting followed, and its input will be analyzed in order to create the last part of the table concerning KPI's (see ANNEX 2.2). Other two workshops are already scheduled. The objective of the second working group workshop, taking place 1st April, is to prioritize these KPI's in order to have a maximum of 2 or 3 KPI's per criterion in order to have a final table that is simple and accessible to all. This will allow each structure to position itself through a common reference grid at the European level in a harmonized way. After finalizing the self-assessment grid and Smart measurable scoring tables, they will be validated in the 3rd workshop on the 29th April 2022 with all the VITALISE partners and the working group participants.

The question of measuring the indicators is an important and difficult point. For some axes there is no objective or quantitative measurement neither reference or a scale. In fact, for each item, the first task is to identify the information available for each indicator:

- either provision of a metric and consideration of the numerical result;
- either provision of an expert evaluation and validation of a rather qualitative indication or a value situated;
- or no information at all, but it is not useful, so it is not taken into consideration, or the opinion of experts is taken.

For this reason, this self-assessment grid serves primarily as a support strategy and not as an evaluation of their status.

At the end of the task, a simple and readable self-assessment grid can be sent to the VITALISE project partners. Also, this self-evaluation grid will be sent to the Living Labs of the ENoLL and LLSA Forum networks to benefit from their feedback during the project. We will ask for feedback from all these structures every 6 months in order to have a continuous improvement process during the rest of the project and to improve the grid in an iterative way. Our objective is that this grid should fit into the economic, geographical and social context of each Living Lab, but preserving also the diversity of all these structures.

Therefore, we are striving throughout VITALISE to have an iterative approach for the evaluation of the procedures within the project (Harmonization methodology) but also beyond the project (the evaluation of all living labs). The approach of a continuous evaluation throughout the remaining duration of the project will allow us to have more concrete feedback, taking into account the possible difficulties and risks.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1

SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONNAIRE

Step 1: Initiation

Decision makers commitment:

Is there a formal statement containing a harmonized vision for the Health and Wellbeing living lab research infrastructures and the appointment of a harmonization coordinator to manage the process?

Harmonization team

Has the core harmonization team been appointed?

Are external consultants needed been appointed?

Has an outline of the full team been defined?

Has a system been defined for collecting and sharing data within the team during the harmonization process?

End of step 1, the 'Initiation' stage: if you are happy with the outcome, move to step 2, otherwise make a list of missing information and corrective actions to be taken, carry out the necessary measures and repeat the first stage in self-assessment

Step 2: Planning

Initial assessment:

Have the procedures and services that are currently being offered by living labs (state of the art) been reviewed at a satisfactorily level and efficiency and effectiveness of current performance assessed?

Has a complete review been carried out of relevant EU/national/regional procedures in living labs?

Has a complete review been carried out of external and internal sources of information used?

Involvement of partners and external stakeholders

Have stakeholders and possible partners been clearly identified?

Has a clear plan for their involvement been drafted?

Have the partners been sufficiently involved and are motivated to do so?

Has the Harmonization process attracted a sufficient number of external stakeholders?

Work plan:

Does the plan for this Sprint contain:

- A clear definition of objectives?
- Actions to be implemented?
- Responsibilities?
- resources needed?
- Timelines?
- Risks and constraints?

End of step 2, the 'Planning' stage: if you are happy with the outcome, move to step 3, otherwise make a list of missing information and corrective actions to be taken, carry out the necessary measures and repeat the second stage in self-assessment

Step 3: Implementation

Share data:

Have appropriate procedures been established for the joint and coordinated collection and elaboration of data on living lab services and procedures?

Has a dedicated space for accessing the data been created and adequate management rules set?

Harmonize items:

Are homogeneous and coherent items contained living lab standard version?

Have all items currently in living lab standard version been reviewed to assess their alignment with the harmonized vision and objectives?

Have all the performed activities in living lab research infrastructure environments been thoroughly examined to define actions with linking items?

End of step 3, the 'Implementation' stage: if you are happy with the outcome, move to step 4, otherwise make a list of missing information and corrective actions to be taken, carry out the necessary measures and repeat the third stage in self-assessment

Step 4: Monitoring and controlling of the harmonization process

How to assess progress of harmonization:

Has the self-assessment questionnaire provided positive results?

Are there corrective and/or preventive actions to be taken?

Has a monitoring plan been produced, aligned with the work-plan?

Is communication with stakeholders envisaged as a relevant element in monitoring procedures?

Step 5: Updating and continuation

Have measures been devised to assess both the impact on Health and Wellbeing living labs sustainability and the effectiveness of the harmonization process?

ANNEX 2

1. Strategy

<i>A. Governance</i>				
Shared vision & mission	Involvement QH4 actors	Team Design	Involvement in local organizations	
			Expected impacts strategy & projects	Participative approach/ open governance
Interviews with separate stakeholder to check if they have the same answers on what is their mission	Implication in public and private networks	Team related skills asked in hiring processes and a clear idea what is needed (HR vision)	Capitalisation of strategic local potential	Degree
Past collaborations linked to vision and mission	Networks/ results of collaborations between QH actors	Diversity of roles in the team (LL roles)	Competitiveness of the LL/ region/ collaborative projects	Stakeholders
Mission and vision are known by the outside world	Main collaborative actions in the past 2 years and outputs/ impacts	Design degrees	Uniqueness and competitiveness of initiative projects	Methodology, methods and tools
Social and ethical values	Open innovation projects	How continuous professional development is ensured? How maintain goal level of innovation through HR practices and functions	Stage of development of regional ecosystem	Citizen engagement and deliberations are present
Shared values	Collaboration models between actors		Providing value to community (linked with business model)	Create a self-assessment tool for confidence levels with participatory design and action methods
Complementary between actors capacities and capabilities			Impact measurement is made concrete, is operationalized in	Commitment with a specific "environment feeling". It means implementation or co-creation of

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

			documents and call for proposals	unique concepts and frameworks we also want to track (defend your innovativeness in participative approach)
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<i>B. Business Model</i>			
Financial engineering	Service portfolio	Status of the organization	
Stakeholders' contributions/ partnerships	Sustainability plans and concretize commitments on next steps to continue consolidating, growing, specialization...	Subsidiaries	
One person actually has a specific role to acquire or design the financial engineering	Level of complementarity to existing offer in our issues	Impact of LL services	
Tool to help to visualize how is the current business economic scheme (per type of funding, set a % and explain), with a second part for "set envisioned plan" if expected changes to come in short medium term	Service development is part of most projects and market up take pilots are visible	Capacity and capabilities used to provide value proposition	
Ideal if this exercise can help to visualize main general players around the economic actual exercise or future planned	Service is "sold" and calculations made on profit services	Innovativeness of LL value proposition	
	Resources that have access to, especially if there are external, and how is the access model/ agreement (e.g. public services, supportive innovation clusters...)	Sustainability (economic) of LL	
	Abilities to self-finance middle, long term	Capacity of business model to integrate other partners	

<i>C. CULTURE</i>			
External collaboration strategy	Internal collaboration strategy	Internal and external communication strategy	Project culture
TRUST degree among stakeholders	Degrees of 3 rd order learning processes	Resilience	Issues knowledge, know how

and LL's, and this is no strategy ;)			
Capacity of Living Lab to attract new collaborators	TRUST degree among stakeholders and LL's, and this is no strategy ;)		Disciplines involved
			Creation date and lifespan
			Soft skills to leverage co-creation in LL

2. Operations

<i>A. Operations</i>			
Experience projects & Activities	Monitoring processes	Branding & positioning	Partner agreements
European projects	Satisfaction survey	Innovation award	ISO
Multi partners	Ethical committee	Local, regional or other geographical focus	NDA
Number of large/ small scale projects	Number of people involved in the data collection for monitoring	Type of Living Lab (public vs private hosted)	Number of partnerships
Duration of the projects	Frequency of the monitoring activities		Types of partners (e.g., SMEs, Research institutions, non profit organization)
Number of follow-up activities to scale up the projects			
Technology Readiness Levels of the project outputs			

<i>B. Human Resources</i>	
Availability & Assignment	Role fluidity
Gender balance	Number of roles assigned during the career
Number of young/ senior professionals	Number of dismissal/ drop out per year
Type and number of training activities for the staff	

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

Number of new professionals recruited every year	
Number of ETP	
Number of Stakeholder	

<i>C. Equipment & Infrastructure</i>	
Access	Availability
Access allowed only to “internal” staff or also to external stakeholders	Type of procedures in place to ask for new/ equipment/ infrastructure
	Procedures to monitor the actual use of the equipment and to understand how to optimize their use
	Number of people in charge of managing the equipment/ infrastructure

3. Openness

<i>A. Innovation processes & partnerships</i>		
Legal agreements	Transparency Lev	Openness (new) partnerships
Number of MoUs with other LLs or companies	Number of non-disclosure agreements for reducing, sharing of information and reduce conflict of interest	Number of partnership agreements with projects or research projects
Number of actual products or licenses/ patents are re-negotiated during the lifetime of the project	Number of communications and promotion of the results	Number of vulnerable groups involved in innovation process life cycle
	Number of user feedback throughout of the life cycle of the project	Number of contracts with PhD students between LLs and other organisations
		Rate of diversity of the actors involved in the partnerships (look at the legal status)
		Number of meetings or email with external people from the living lab to increase knowledge sharing (perhaps move it to impact & value?)
		Rate of diversity in the team responsible for the innovation process

<i>B. Ownership of results</i>			
Generation of content/ Feedback protection	Types of ownership	IP processes	Data agreements
IPR of knowledge produced	Number of copyrights	Number of patents	Number of data agreements in place
Number of laws changed thanks to the resulted produced		Number of licenses awarded	
		Shared IP backgrounds	

4. User & Reality

<i>A. Lifecycle & real-life</i>	
Lifecycle/ integrative process	Real-life settings
In which phases of the innovation are users actively involved	Where does the UI take place?
Are all phases covered in the LL project	

<i>B. User</i>		
Intensity	Representativity	Permanence user panel
The level of influence/ power of users on LL project & activities	The level of how user panel represents the LL ecosystem	Does it exist?
The level of involvement of users (how many/ often)	Are the users really representing themselves?	Heterogeneity
User roles (e.g., also project meeting?)	Are the users experts or non-experts on the subject	Size the panel
In which phases of the innovation are users actively involved	Number of vulnerable groups involved in the innovation process life cycle	

<i>C. Tools & Methods</i>			
Engagement strategies	Range tools & Methods	Quality & innovativeness	External communication processes
Incentives (vouchers)	How many different types	User roles (e.g. also project meeting)	Newsletters
Being taken seriously (intrinsic)	Quantitative vs qualitative		Social media

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

Sharing results	Multi method approach (how well are tools adapted to the selected method)		Events
Explain results & their usage (what we will use for it)			Workshops
			Webinars
			Internal community team assigned

5. Impact and value

<i>A. Co-created values</i>						
User satisfaction	Stakeholder satisfaction	Knowledge exchange & sharing	Academic validation	Capacity building	Value capturing strategies	Value chain coverage
Meaningful and useful solutions LL and solution respecting my integrity, freedom	Translation of user 'needs' in a language that make sense to the different stakeholders	Large work projects investments	Publication	Number of work experiences		Through its methodologies
Number of requests (if they come back request for our work)	Interaction	Number of open scientific publications	Number of diplomas	Versatility		
Standard questionnaire on user satisfaction agreed among all LL	Participation to events	Originality and added value of the solution which regards to existing solutions on the market	Professionals' academic levels	Regarding human resources : vision, value and specific methodology of the LL		
Active participation	Invitations coming from the	Number of open	Number of publication	Number of new team members		

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

during meetings	stakeholders	workshops/webinars organized	involving LL	that are involved in the LL activities		
Participation in events (ratio/participated/invited)	Standard questionnaire on user satisfaction agreed among all LL	Number of relevant materials shared through their website (standard way of sharing material such as 'projects deliverables')				

<i>B. Impacts</i>				
Internal impact	Societal impact	Economical impact	Environmental impact	Regulatory impact
Sustainable economic model	Recognition	Participation rate in the economy	Number of actions implemented in favour of the environment	Number of recommendations shared with external (public) organisations
Number of external researchers (belonging to the same organisation) started considering LL methodology for their project (change of cultural with the organisation)	User behaviour change	Number of investments		Number of organisations agreeing with recommendations
Development of innovative research perspective	Freedom of choice of end-users (citizen patients, older people...)	LL stakeholder (SME, NGO's, business) impact (monetary and non-monetary e.g. influence on strategies)		
	Number of projects/activities linked to the local	Job creation		

	community challenges			
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6. Stability & Harmonization

<i>A. Stability</i>		
SWOT	Improved collaborations	Business plan
Use the 4 criteria in a confrontation-matrix check with your VISION strategic goal (e.g., 3 yearly)	Number of strategic partnerships (long term collaborations)	% of private and public funding
KPIs are adapted based on strategic goals and subgoals	Rate the internal collaboration in terms of funding, what's in it for them, quantity what you mean to them	Risk of revenue items
Sustainability items	Which, how collaborations ensure sustainability & meeting KPIs	Revenue items Cash flows Cash management
Revenue streams	Value and impact part of each collaboration	Continuous revenue items (low risk)
Distinction of sustainability and growth in SWOT	Direct collaborations that bring short term value	Occasional revenue streams (e.g., projects) – high risk
Growth items	Long-term collaborations that bring value to the long term	What is your USP? (check with SWOT)
Growth in expertise (topics, team, methodologies)		
Relevance to vision, mission, strategy		

<i>B. Harmonization & scale-up</i>			
Standardization (harmonization?)	Replicability	Cross-border, cross-sectoral	Benchmark knowledge sharing & capacity building
Minimum communication channels	KPI: Rate the usability and added value of these standard tools (by all organisations/ living labs using them)	Speak the 'same language'	Best practices
BP Format	Performance management systems	Make sure the tools can be used across thematic domains (check with stakeholders and map with context)	Quality and quantity of materials produced and used

D2.2 Evaluation process and tools

SWOT Format	Strategic Planning Format	KPI: amount of cross-border collaborations between living labs (mature and start-ups)	Training materials
Standard toolbox/ methodologies with proven track record/ quality assurance	Stakeholder defining format	Learn by doing	Provide experience back to the LL community
Ensure serendipity of LL	Minimum resources	Networking (ENoLL, EIT Health...)	Virtual learning labs
Make sure there is enough room for creativity (for innovation of these standard tools)		Knowledge transfer in publications and collaborations	